

DISTENDER D8.1 User Requirements

D8.1: User Requirements
WP 8, T 8.1

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1 Introduction

This document is a formal deliverable of the DISTENDER project and was developed within Work Package 8: Decision Support System, Task 8.1: DSS Requirements.

The purpose of this document is to define the user requirements concerning a Decision Support System (DSS) aimed to support decision-makers in planning the activity of adaptation and mitigation strategies in response to the climate change.

The requirements will be treated as valid recommendations concerning the usability of the system at the development stage of the Decision Support System. The software design process will follow a User Centred Design approach (UCD). The user requirements gathering is the first stage of this approach and has its source in the needs, characteristics, and abilities of the users. Therefore, determining who will use the system is very important. Understanding the user and his needs gives a basis for analysing how the system should be designed and what functionalities it should have to ensure that it will be used in an effective, efficient, safe, and satisfying manner.

The user requirements specified here will be subject to further verification. Not all of the requirements may be considered as relevant and used during implementation. Their feasibility in terms of budget limitations, human resources (PM), and technical constraints will be taken into account. During the verification process, it should be analysed whether the implementation of individual requirements will affect other elements of the system negatively, disturb its cohesion, or reduce user-friendliness and usability. It will be done as part of the design task.

The general structure of the document is as follows:

- Chapter 2 – Terms and acronyms – provides a list of acronyms and terms used throughout this document.
- Chapter 3 - System overview – provides a description of the system, modes of operation, and defines its users.
- Chapter 4 - Requirements collection – describes the process and work of gathering user requirements. The respondents and a short summary of the questionnaire as well as potential scenarios of use are presented.
- Chapter 5 – Requirements – is the main part of this document. The collected requirements are grouped and presented in a tabular form.
- Chapter 6 - Conclusions.

2 Terms and acronyms

This part defines the technical terms used in this document.

2.1 Terms

Table 1: List of terms

Term	Explanation/definition
Action/measure	An individual approach taken to address mitigation/ adaptation or other goals within a case study.
Case Study	Case studies developed within the project (Core Case Studies) or individual ones, developed after the project.
Core Case Studies (CCS)	Five case studies developed within the project, describing the strategy taken for adaptation to climate change. The case studies show how robust decisions can be made based on the knowledge and information provided by the models used in DISTENDER.
Case Study User	A user of the system for whom targeted strategies were developed (within the process of modelling during the DISTENDER project or after the project).
Climate change indicator	A specific, observable and measurable characteristic/ parameter used to show state, changes, or progress in the area of climate change and its influences on the economy.
Decision making process	All activities of conceptualization, analysis, and planning, ended with making a decision and choosing the most efficient public initiatives/actions.
Decision Support System (DSS)	A software system which performs a function of advising which alternative set of initiatives are the most efficient ones to achieve a certain goal. It is a tool that supports decision makers in the development of adaptation and mitigation strategies, integrating DISTENDER results.
Indicator	A specific, observable and measurable characteristic/ parameter used to show state, changes, or progress in a certain area.
Initiative	A policy, programme, strategy, plan, or any other kind of activity aiming at adaptation and/or mitigation of climate change effects and their impact.
Impact model	A DISTENDER impact model provided for a specific domain: air quality and emissions, urban heat island, health, energy, water, or AFOLU (Agriculture, Forestry, and Other Land Use)

Mitigation and adaptation measure	A measure/action which aims to mitigate or adapt to the climate change consequences.
New User	A user of the system who wants to try how the system works, and for whom the robust strategies (within the process of modelling) have not been developed. Such a user works on the data produced within CCS publicly available.
Robust strategy	A strategy adopted in a case study which is robust (e.g. feasible and effective) across a range of climatic and socioeconomic futures.
Scenario	A planned or expected sequence of events that occurs as a result of implementing a specific strategy.
Socio-economic scenario	A scenario developed for a core case study until 2050, covering the city itself or a broader region, relating to a broad set of drivers (including technological, political, institutional, and cultural factors) and being largely qualitative.
Strategy/Pathway	A combination of actions/measures/interventions taken to address case study goals for adaptation and mitigation to climate change. Strategy and pathway are used as synonyms.
Use case	A presentation of a possible usage of the system in the form of a sequence of simple steps.
User	A Case Study User or a New User.

2.2 Acronyms

Table 2: List of acronyms

Acronyms	Description
AFOLU	Agriculture, Forestry, and Other Land Use
CC	Climate Change
CCS	Core Case Studies
DSS	Decision Support System
IT	Information Technology
MCDA	Multi-Criteria Decision Analysis
UCD	User Centred Design approach
UIX	User Interface XML
XML	Extensible Markup Language

3 System overview

This chapter is an introduction to the concept of the DSS system. Information about the DDS, its functionalities, and tasks that it is expected to support is presented here, as well as the information flow between the user and the system.

3.1 Description of the system

Decision support systems are systems that provide tools, information, and knowledge, used in decision-making, mainly by middle and high-level management and planning analysts. The main task of decision support systems is to provide processed, accurate information which authorities, managers, or analysts can use while making strategic, tactical, or operational decisions. The functions of decision support systems include also preparation of decision variants as well as supporting the selection of the optimal variant of acting (primarily in making strategic and tactical decisions). They are applicable mainly in situations where there is a high risk of making a mistake incurring significant costs.

One of the results of the DISTENDER project will be a dedicated Decision Support System (DSS). The DSS will be a software application supporting decision makers in developing adaptation and mitigation strategies being a response to climate change. It will integrate DISTENDER results. The system will not make decisions for the user, but will present a set of information to support the decision-making process.

The system will operate on the data that will be generated in the project as a result of the following activities:

- a) Identification of the consequences of the scenario where the future climate is materializing in today's socio-economic system;
- b) Identification of the consequences, if the future climate is materializing in a possible future socio-economic system that follows current existing policies;
- c) Identification of a set of strategies, which will be simulated under the local socio-economic-climate scenarios;
- d) Production of the corresponding socio-economic parameters and the land use associated to each strategy;
- e) Generation of the quantitative information about positive and negative effects in a future climate and socio-economic system;
- f) Modelling robust strategies for each sector (AFOLU, air quality and emissions, health, energy, water).

The results of the simulations will be an input for the DSS stored in the form of indicators and numerical data. These data will be subject to a multi-criteria decision analysis, carried out by the system as a consequence of a system user's activity. The groups of such indicators are presented in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Groups of indicators to be implemented as the initial data into the system

Figure 2 presents the information flow between the user and the system. First the user (i.e. a policy maker) creates his/her own Case Study or chooses one of the predefined DISTENDER CCS. Next, the user sets his/her preferences by selection of the strategies and sending requests to the DSS platform (setting preferences). The requests are processed within the MCDA in order to find the relevant results (strategies) in the database. The system provides the user with a set of ordered detailed strategies. For each strategy, the user can see the impact on a specific sector, applied mitigation and adaptation measures, and socio-business-climate consequences which will occur if the specific strategy is applied.

Figure 2: Data flow in the DSS

3.2 Users of the system

User requirements have their source in the needs and abilities of users and in user case characteristics. Therefore, it is crucial to determine who is going to use the system. Understanding the user needs provides a strong basis for analysing how the system should be designed and what functionality it should deliver.

To determine the system end user, attention was paid to the subject of the project, its specificity, and the type of input and output data, which will be the basis for the system's operations.

Taking the above into consideration, **the main end-users will be the bodies interested in evaluating, developing, or integrating adaptation and mitigation strategies in the areas of the economy affected by climate change.** As the main function of the system is to support the decision-making process, special attention was paid to persons who are decision-makers and who provide support in the decision-making process at any governmental level to improve the adaptation and mitigation capacity of cities and regions (from national to regional and local). An example of system users are the employees of the ministries, their departments, and government agencies. The decisions they make may concern for example implementing a climate strategy in a regional scale, or defining measures to mitigate or avoid the consequences of climate change.

During the project and when it ends, the main users of the system will be the policy makers supported by the DISTENDER stakeholders who are able to work on scenarios and strategies generated in the specific Core Case Studies. After the end of the project, the DSS should provide access to the publicly available results of DISTENDER to other policy-makers representatives to use the system, mainly by searching, presenting results and also creating specific case study by new users.

3.3 Modes of operation

The main requirement on the system is to support the decision-making process. The system will provide end users with the knowledge and capabilities necessary to develop their own tailored socio-economic and climate scenarios including the impact assessment. These scenarios will contain the models to produce the required indicators. The system should recommend which alternative set of initiatives/actions/measures are the most efficient ones for achieving the user's (decision maker's) goal. It should also present how the application of specific measures (taking specific actions) affects other aspects of the economy (sectors) and climate over the years.

The system will have two modes of operation:

1. The first one is dedicated to the users for whom data is developed as part of the work in the DISTENDER project (or simulated as part of ordering such a service after the end of the project);
2. The second mode is dedicated to the users who enter their own data into the system to define their individual case studies (they did not order any simulations/scenarios/impact models).

Two main use cases following this approach were developed and are presented in Figure 3 and Figure 4.

Figure 3: Use case for an already developed Case Study

Figure 4: Use case for a new case study

The presented use cases were the basis for further analysis of the system in terms of its functionality and requirements and applicability by the users.

4 Requirements collection

Collecting information related to user requirements was carried out in a two-pronged way. On the one hand, information was gathered during meetings with the project partners, where the vision of the system and its purpose were consulted. On the other hand, consultations with representatives of the Core Case Studies (CCS) were carried out. The representatives of the CCS were also a connection point in collecting information from potential users of the system, in particular from policy-makers at various levels of the decision-making process. One of the methods to collect information from users was a survey distributed by the CCS representatives.

All the results from the interviews and the questionnaires are collected in the form of tables included in Chapter 5.

4.1 Respondents and their selection

The respondents of the survey were potential users of the DSS from the CCS. This included the staff of government agencies including policy-makers (local government offices: municipalities, regional agencies), NGOs and research organisations involved in making decisions about climate change adaptation and/or mitigation programmes in each CCS. Answers from 12 respondents were collected. This involvement may be at any stage from an idea to the final decision of its implementation.

The survey was addressed primarily to the CCS representatives, because they will be the users/customers of the system. The system will provide the results of modelling and simulation of the strategies defined for their cases. The CCS representatives act for the following institutions:

- Federal Ministry for Climate Action, Environment, Energy, Mobility, Innovation and Technology (Austria),
- Metropolitan City of Turin,
- European Agroforestry Federation,
- Municipio de Guimarães,
- Hanze University Groningen.

The CCS representatives, based on their best knowledge and contact channels, distributed the survey within their networks (mainly to policy makers and those who are involved in the policy making process, provide alternatives, decide on which alternatives should be presented to the decision makers).

4.2 Questionnaire verifying the usefulness of the DSS

In order to collect as many answers as possible from potential users of the system, a dedicated questionnaire was formulated. The survey was developed in a Google Docs form in order to be easy to share and available, and it was divided into the following sections:

- A. Glossary (prepared in order to explain the terms used in the survey),

- B. Respondent's profile (in this section the respondents were asked to provide the basic information about their position and responsibilities),
- C. Decision making process (this part aimed to understand the current way of proceeding/procedures related to decision making),
- D. Decision Support (this section contained the questions related to general use of software tools in the decision making process),
- E. DSS as a DISTENDER tool (this part contained a description of the DSS, use cases of potential applications of the system; the questions asked here aimed at collecting as many user requirements as possible and understanding the user needs).

4.3 Potential scenarios of use/use cases of the DSS

For the purposes of a better understanding of the system by the users and presenting them the potential opportunities, some examples of what the decision support system could be used for were developed. Such examples were described from the user's perspective to introduce the end users to the terms of the DSS and verify their expectations/needs towards the system. The following scenarios were presented to the respondents:

1. Finding measures leading to a given goal
 - a. Description from the user's perspective: I have to do something, adapt some mitigation and adaptation measures (M&A measures) to achieve my goal. I am wondering what measures could be applied and how they will affect certain aspects of the city/environment/urban planning etc.
 - b. Example: I have to do something to reduce the CO₂ emissions in my city. I would like to know the list of the available M&A measures and would like to know how they affect some aspects of the city, environment, climate, society, or economy.
2. Finding measures to reach a desired/specified state/effect
 - a. Description from the user's perspective: I have to achieve an exact number/exact level of one of the indicators; what should I do to achieve this goal?
 - b. Example: because of some recommendations from the government, I have to reduce CO₂ emissions by 30% in 10 years. What should I do to achieve this level?
3. Finding measures leading to a given goal to the highest possible extent
 - a. Description from the user's perspective: I would like to know which M&A measures I should apply in order to achieve my goal in the most efficient way.
 - b. Example: which mitigation and adaptation measures would be the most efficient in reducing CO₂ emissions?
4. Finding the consequences of given measures
 - a. Description from the user's perspective: I know which M&A measures I am going to apply. I would like to know the consequences of applying a specific measure.
 - b. Example: I have to eliminate cars with internal combustion engines from the city. What effects will it bring?
5. Finding the consequences of inaction
 - a. Description from the user's perspective: I want to know what will happen if I do not implement specific M&A measures.

- b. Example: I cannot afford (e.g. for financial reasons) to eliminate combustion cars from the city. What will happen? How will it increase greenhouse gases in the city? How will it affect the incidence of respiratory diseases?

Moreover, an attempt was made to visualize the anticipated fundamental functions of the DSS. The visualization was broken down into steps that the user could follow if the system was designed in a given way. The first mock-ups were presented, and were further updated during the joint discussion.

4.4 Summary

The activities described in this chapter resulted in the collection of information constituting the basis for formulating the user requirements for the decision support system which were presented in Chapter 5.

The results of the surveys conducted among the CCS representatives and users involved in the decision-making process (including decision-makers) provide a set of information useful from the system design point of view.

Firstly, the responders give an insight into the complexity of the decision-making process, which begins with defining the goals to be achieved, proceeds with collecting and analysing data, assessing expected values, analysing different scenarios, and ends with defining the best strategies and adopting the necessary measures. Deciding where the DSS fits within this spectrum will be an important aspect of the next phase of the DSS work.

Secondly, the CCS respondents' indicate what data the respondents work with in the decision-making procedure. These are mainly historical data, and analyses of decisions made by others in similar situations (see the Figure 5).

Figure 5: The type of data that respondents work with in the decision-making process

Another issue depicted by the results of the survey is the support that a software tool can offer in the decision-making process. The responses clearly show that a decision support tool can be helpful both in the initial phase of decision-making (impact analysis, risk and financial analysis, selection and planning of actions) and in the implementation phase

(checkpoint assessment, reassessment of validation, implementation). These results were presented on the Figure 6 and Figure 7.

Figure 6: Usefulness of the software tool at the initial stage of the decision making process

Figure 7: Usefulness of the software tool at the realisation stage of the decision making process

The most important part in the questionnaire regarding the user requirements for the DISTENDER DSS was a group of questions related to presenting the examples of DISTENDER usage and scenarios of use. The answers to these questions indicate that the respondents expect the DSS to present the consequences of applying the selected measures/strategy. They also want to be informed about the effects of inaction. The potential users need support in finding appropriate mitigation and adaptation measures which lead them to achieve their goal. Considering the functionalities that the system should provide, the respondents indicate the need for a comprehensive report, with a presentation of simulations and scenarios that will take place when they follow a specific strategy (see the Figure 8)

Figure 8: The most useful functionalities of the system

Another method of collecting the user requirements (i.e. meetings and consultations with the project partners and the CCS representatives) provided an outline of the functionality of the DISTENDER DSS under development in terms of both the needs of the CCS and the limitations that result from the data provided by the project partners.

A result of these activities, in addition to the collected user requirements, is updated mock-up reflecting the way the system works (presented in the Chapter 6).

5 Requirements

This section presents the requirements grouped into several categories. Each requirement is described using a table with the following fields:

- ID - unique identifier, (not related to the content of requirement or schedule to be implemented),
- Title - short name of the requirement, indicating its purpose,
- Priority - importance of the requirement; possible values: High/Medium/Low,
- Type - requirement type (explained below),
- Description - additional information about the requirement,
- Source - origin of the requirement.

Table 3: Template used for the user requirement description.

ID:		Title:	
Priority:		Type:	
Description:			
Source:			

The prioritization was based on the MoSCoW method, however, the authors of the document decided whether the requirement was high (must have), medium (should have) or low (could have). It was assumed that the requirement is:

- high when was defined on the basis of the Description of the action records, or comes from other sources but is in line with Description of the action;
- medium when comes from the partners of the consortium or respondents (potential users) and is important but not necessary for functioning of the system;
- low when is desirable by the partners of the consortium or respondents but not necessary; taken into account during system implementation, can improve the user experience or satisfaction.

The classification of the requirement types is as follows:

- Functional - requirement which describes some actions which should be performed by the system: the fundamental or essential subject matter of the product. It describes what the system has to do or what processing actions it is to take.
- Non-functional - requirement which describes some system parameters: the properties that the system functions need to have, such as performance or usability.

Sources:

- Partners within the consortium (excluding CCS representatives),
- Description of the action – the needs and requirements stated in the Description of the action of the project,
- Users – a need expressed by the potential users of the DSS service (respondents, including CCS representatives),

Within the requirements defined so far (84), most of them concern output data requirements, defined in the vast majority by system users. The numerical presentation of the collected requirements is presented in the Table 4.

Table 4 Requirements in numbers

Category	Quantity	Priority			Main Source
		High	Medium	Low	
General	14	14	0	0	Description of the action
Data acquisition and processing	9	8	1	0	Partners within the consortium
Initial data	4	4	0	0	Partners within the consortium
Input data	6	4	2	0	Partners within the consortium
Output data	29	10	16	3	Users
Multi-criteria analysis	4	2	2	0	Description of the action
Dissemination, exploitation and commercialisation	5	3	2	0	Description of the action/Authors
Others	13	1	9	3	Authors of the document
Sum	84	46	32	6	-

5.1 General

This section contains general requirements that apply to the product (DSS) as a whole. It includes also the business requirements.

ID:	G01	Title:	Give support to decision makers in developing strategies
Priority:	High	Type:	Functional
Description:	The system shall support decision makers in developing adaptation planning process and mitigation strategies, integrating the outcomes of the various WPs in the DSS.		
Source:	Description of the action (page 83)		

ID:	G02	Title:	Enable users to elaborate their own scenarios
Priority:	High	Type:	Functional
Description:	The system shall provide end users with the information needed to develop their own tailored socio-economic and climate scenarios including the impact assessment models to produce the required indicators.		
Source:	Description of the action (page 116)		

ID:	G03	Title:	Integrating the results
Priority:	High	Type:	Functional
Description:	The DSS shall integrate the knowledge generated by the DISTENDER project, especially the three key elements and associated methods: (i) context-specific climate and socio-economic scenarios, (ii) risk and vulnerability assessment and (iii) cost-benefit assessment.		
Source:	Description of the action (page 116)		

ID:	G04	Title:	Availability in a form of a common platform
Priority:	High	Type:	Non-functional
Description:	The DSS shall constitute a common platform for stakeholders.		
Source:	Description of the action (page 116)		

ID:	G05	Title:	Supporting transferability, scalability and replicability
Priority:	High	Type:	Functional
Description:	The DSS shall follow the harmonised approach to data collection across the different case studies to support transferability, scalability and replicability of DISTENDER methodologies in different EU contexts.		
Source:	Description of the action (page 84)		

ID:	G06	Title:	List of optimal strategies
Priority:	High	Type:	Functional
Description:	The DSS shall provide the user with a list of optimal strategies by applying a multi-criteria approach.		
Source:	Description of the action (page 117)		

ID:	G07	Title:	Development based on the results
Priority:	High	Type:	Non-functional
Description:	The system shall be developed on the basis of the modelling results, the previously developed scenarios, and the designed strategies.		
Source:	Partners within the consortium		

ID:	G08	Title:	Leading the user to define his target
Priority:	High	Type:	Functional
Description:	The system shall offer a choice of options that will lead the user to define his target, which is the subject of the decision to be made.		
Source:	Partners within the consortium		

ID:	G09	Title:	Evaluate options and prioritize actions
Priority:	High	Type:	Functional
Description:	The DSS shall enable the user to appraise tailored options (addressing effectiveness, feasibility, affordability, etc.) and prioritizing actions to best allocate funds.		
Source:	Description of the action (page 117)		

ID:	G10	Title:	Organising and visualising information, analysing trader offs and synergies
Priority:	High	Type:	Non-functional
Description:	The DSS shall help decision makers to organize and visualize information, analyze potential trade-offs and synergies supported by quantitative and qualitative analysis		
Source:	Description of the action (page 116)		

ID:	G11	Title:	Providing guidance: Downscaling climate scenarios and uncertainties
Priority:	High	Type:	Non-functional
Description:	The Decision Support System (DSS) will guide how to downscale climate scenarios and context-specific socio-economic scenarios to project foresee climatic conditions and associated uncertainties for third parties (replication).		
Source:	Description of the action (page 118)		

ID:	G12	Title:	Allowing assessment of CC adaptation and mitigation strategies
Priority:	High	Type:	Non-functional
Description:	DSS shall allow future stakeholders to assess CC adaptation and mitigation strategies over different sectors concerning changes of environmental and socio-economic conditions during the next decades.		
Source:	Description of the action (page 117)		

ID:	G13	Title:	Help in analysing data
Priority:	High	Type:	Non-functional
Description:	DSS shall help local administrations to analyse data about the effect of CC and to assess, prioritize and finance mitigation and adaptation measures.		
Source:	Description of the action (page 128)		

ID:	G14	Title:	Integrating top-down and bottom up approaches into a multi-scale framework
Priority:	High	Type:	Non-functional
Description:	Decision Support System (DSS) platform supporting cross-sectorial integrating top-down and bottom-up approaches into a multi-scale framework to examine cross-scale interactions of climate adaptation and mitigation actions		
Source:	Description of the action (page 143)		

5.2 Data acquisition and processing

This part presents the requirements specifying the source of the data which are processed by the system to be useful for the user.

ID:	DP01	Title:	Processing environmental characteristics
Priority:	High	Type:	Non-functional
Description:	The DSS shall process data concerning natural environment characteristics, local and global climate trends including climate models (publicly accessible).		
Source:	Partners within the consortium		

ID:	DP02	Title:	Processing socio-economics statistics, factors, pathways, and scenarios
Priority:	High	Type:	Non-functional
Description:	The DSS shall process socio-economics statistics, factors, pathways, and scenarios (present and future, publicly accessible).		
Source:	Partners within the consortium		

ID:	DP03	Title:	Threats, risks, and vulnerabilities data processing
Priority:	High	Type:	Non-functional
Description:	The DSS shall work on data related to threats, risks, and vulnerabilities of the main domains of impact (publicly accessible).		
Source:	Partners within the consortium		

ID:	DP04	Title:	Impact model data processing
Priority:	High	Type:	Non-functional
Description:	The DSS shall process data coming from impact models including agriculture, energy production and distribution, urban planning, water management, air quality control, health care, etc. (publicly accessible).		
Source:	Partners within the consortium		

ID:	DP05	Title:	User administration and application set-up data
Priority:	High	Type:	Non-functional
Description:	The DSS shall process user administration and application set-up data.		
Source:	Partners within the consortium		

ID:	DP06	Title:	Using specific algorithm to process data
Priority:	Medium	Type:	Non-functional
Description:	The DSS should use a two-step data estimation algorithm to close data gaps in a statistical way.		
Source:	Partners within the consortium		

ID:	DP07	Title:	Indicator data processing
Priority:	High	Type:	Non-functional
Description:	The DSS shall process data coming from the indicators derived from the modelling WPs (WP3, WP4, WP5, WP7)		
Source:	Description of action (page 133)		

ID:	DP08	Title:	No classified information processing
Priority:	High	Type:	Non-functional
Description:	The DSS shall not process any classified information, confidential or personal data.		
Source:	Description of action (page 154)		

ID:	DP09	Title:	Quantitative and qualitative data processing
Priority:	High	Type:	Non-functional
Description:	The system shall process the initial data which are both quantitative and qualitative.		
Source:	Partners within the consortium		

5.3 Initial data

This part encloses all the requirements related to the data which will be included in the system and displayed to the user while he provides his input. The user will work with these data to receive the results.

ID:	ID01	Title:	Working with data defining robust strategies
Priority:	High	Type:	Non-functional
Description:	The system shall work with data determining robust strategies. These data will be provided in a form of numerical data.		
Source:	Partners within the consortium		

ID:	ID02	Title:	Displaying the list of CCS
Priority:	High	Type:	Functional
Description:	The system shall display the list of Core Case Studies developed within the DISTENDER project.		
Source:	Partners within the consortium		

ID:	ID03	Title:	Displaying the list of robust strategies
Priority:	High	Type:	Functional
Description:	The system shall display the list of robust strategies developed for either the Core Case Study or the specific new Case Study.		
Source:	Partners within the consortium		

ID:	ID04	Title:	Enabling the user to define his preferences
Priority:	High	Type:	Functional
Description:	The system shall provide the user with the list of specific questions to define his preferences (regarding his ability/needs to take appropriate measures).		
Source:	Partners within the consortium		

5.4 Input data

This section gathers the requirements regarding the data that the user must enter into the system in order to generate a specific result. It may include for example the method of providing such data (a drop-down list, the possibility of entering his own data, the possibility to choose some indicators, etc.).

ID:	IN01	Title:	Entering data to specify one's own Case Study
Priority:	Medium	Type:	Functional
Description:	The system shall allow a New User to enter data to define his own Case Study.		
Source:	Partners within the consortium		

ID:	IN02	Title:	Selecting one of the previously defined Case Studies
Priority:	Medium	Type:	Functional
Description:	The system shall enable the Case Study User to choose one of the previously defined Case Studies		
Source:	Partners within the consortium		

ID:	IN03	Title:	Providing synthetic data
Priority:	Medium	Type:	Functional
Description:	The system should provide a New User with the synthetic data which are most similar to his predefined Case Study.		
Source:	Partners within the consortium		

ID:	IN04	Title:	Enabling the user to work with data released for public use
Priority:	High	Type:	Functional
Description:	The system shall allow a user to work with publicly available data developed in the DISTENDER project.		
Source:	Partners within the consortium		

ID:	IN05	Title:	Selection of robust strategies
Priority:	High	Type:	Functional
Description:	The system shall allow the user to select robust strategies developed for a particular Case Study.		
Source:	Partners within the consortium		

ID:	IN06	Title:	Allowing the user to enter answers to questions
Priority:	High	Type:	Functional
Description:	The system shall allow the user to provide answers to questions in order to determine his preferences (concerning the possibility/need to take appropriate action).		
Source:	Partners within the consortium		

5.5 Output data (results)

In this part the requirements specified for the results that the system provides to the user are presented. They, for example, indicate how the results should be displayed to satisfy the potential user of the system.

ID:	OD01	Title:	Offering the set of adaptation and mitigation measures/actions
Priority:	High	Type:	Functional
Description:	The DSS shall allow the user to select a set of adaptation and mitigation measures he/she may apply to reach his goal.		
Source:	Partners within the consortium		

ID:	OD02	Title:	Provision of robust strategies to Case Study User
Priority:	High	Type:	Functional
Description:	For a Case Study User, the system shall provide the list of robust strategies.		
Source:	Partners within the consortium		

ID:	OD03	Title:	Provision of most similar strategies to a new user
Priority:	High	Type:	Functional
Description:	For a New User the system shall allow to select/define the robust strategies most similar to the user case.		
Source:	Partners within the consortium		

ID:	OD04	Title:	Presenting a list of robust strategies
Priority:	High	Type:	Functional
Description:	After the user defines his preferences, the system shall generate a list of strategies.		
Source:	Partners within the consortium		

ID:	OD05	Title:	Displaying ordered robust strategies
Priority:	High	Type:	Functional
Description:	The robust strategies shall be ranked according to their compliance with the user's preferences.		
Source:	Partners within the consortium		

ID:	OD06	Title:	Comparing the strategies
Priority:	Medium	Type:	Functional
Description:	The system should enable the user to compare selected strategies		
Source:	Users		

ID:	OD07	Title:	Presentation of specific information within the strategy
Priority:	High	Type:	Functional
Description:	After choosing a strategy, the system shall provide a set of information presenting how the application of specific measures (taking specific actions) will affect other aspects of the economy (sectors) and socio-economic life over the years.		
Source:	Partners within the consortium/users		

ID:	OD08	Title:	Displaying the report
Priority:	Medium	Type:	Functional
Description:	The system should offer a function of generating a comprehensive report on the obtained results.		
Source:	Users		

ID:	OD09	Title:	Filtering mechanism for reports
Priority:	Medium	Type:	Functional
Description:	The user should be able to use filters to receive only the desired information in the report.		
Source:	Authors of the document		

ID:	OD10	Title:	Visualization of possible climate change
Priority:	Medium	Type:	Functional
Description:	The possible CC/other impact should be visualized on a map with a transparent layer in a particular colour. The visualized data will depend on external providers.		
Source:	Users/Partners within the consortium		

ID:	OD11	Title:	Displaying data on maps
Priority:	Medium	Type:	Functional
Description:	Part of the results shall be displayed on the map showing the changes over the years.		
Source:	Users		

ID:	OD12	Title:	Comprehensible and intuitive format of results
Priority:	Medium	Type:	Non-functional
Description:	The recommendations given by the DSS should be provided in a comprehensible and intuitive format so the users are able to work with the results outside the DSS.		
Source:	Partners within the consortium		

ID:	OD13	Title:	Presentation of scenarios to a new user
Priority:	Medium	Type:	Functional
Description:	The system should present to the New User the results of the application of the measures (strategy) to the case most similar to user's.		
Source:	Users		

ID:	OD14	Title:	Presentation of scenarios to Case Studies Users
Priority:	High	Type:	Functional
Description:	The system shall present to the Case Study User the simulations/scenarios of the application of the specified mitigation and adaptation measures (strategy) resulting from the modelling process conducted for the specific Case Study.		
Source:	Partners within the consortium		

ID:	OD15	Title:	Exporting GIS format data
Priority:	Medium	Type:	Functional
Description:	The system should be able to export GIS data.		
Source:	Users		

ID:	OD16	Title:	Infographics presentation
Priority:	Low	Type:	Functional
Description:	The system may present the results in a form of infographics.		
Source:	Users		

ID:	OD17	Title:	Presenting consequences of inaction
Priority:	Medium	Type:	Functional
Description:	The system should provide the consequences of applying a specific measure or indicator.		
Source:	Users		

ID:	OD18	Title:	Presentation of impact on many sectors
Priority:	Medium	Type:	Functional
Description:	The presented results of application of the selected robust strategy should take into account many sectors.		
Source:	Partners within the consortium		

ID:	OD19	Title:	Presenting a list of non-robust strategies
Priority:	Low	Type:	Functional
Description:	The system may provide not only the results coming from the robust strategies, but also strategies that were not modelled. These strategies may be provided with a short description or explanation why they are not robust or why these measures are excluded.		
Source:	Partners within the consortium		

ID:	OD20	Title:	Format of data generated from the project
Priority:	Medium	Type:	Non-functional
Description:	The system should provide data in a format useful to the users, mainly xls, png, pdf, GIS, mapviewer, csv, netcdf.		
Source:	Users		

ID:	OD21	Title:	Providing analysis of impact
Priority:	Medium	Type:	Functional
Description:	The system should provide the the results of impact analysis.		
Source:	Users		

ID:	OD22	Title:	Providing financial analysis
Priority:	Medium	Type:	Functional
Description:	The system should provide financial analysis.		
Source:	Users		

ID:	OD23	Title:	Data presented in a format to be implemented in another system
Priority:	Low	Type:	Functional
Description:	The system may work with data which can be easily implemented to another system in the user's institution.		
Source:	Users		

ID:	OD24	Title:	Sharing results
Priority:	Medium	Type:	Functional
Description:	The system should give the possibility to share data with other users or export them.		
Source:	Users		

ID:	OD25	Title:	Presenting measures leading to achieving a specific goal
Priority:	Medium	Type:	Functional
Description:	The system should present the measures to be taken for obtaining a specific level of an indicator.		
Source:	Users		

ID:	OD26	Title:	Showing most effective measures
Priority:	Medium	Type:	Functional
Description:	The system should indicate which measures bring the fastest effect.		
Source:	Users		

ID:	OD27	Title:	Presenting consequences of a specific action
Priority:	Medium	Type:	Functional
Description:	The system should present the consequences of applying the given measures.		
Source:	Users		

ID:	OD28	Title:	Providing results in specific forms
Priority:	Medium	Type:	Non-functional
Description:	The system should provide maps, diagrams, graphs, illustrations, maps in QGIS format, and Excel spreadsheets.		
Source:	Users		

ID:	OD29	Title:	Presenting advantages and disadvantages of a given strategy
Priority:	Medium	Type:	Functional
Description:	The system should provide a list of advantages and disadvantages resulting from implementing a specific strategy.		
Source:	Partners within the consortium		

5.6 Multi-criteria analysis

In this part the expectations regarding the multi-criteria analysis were collected.

ID:	MCA01	Title:	Supporting strategy selection process
Priority:	High	Type:	Non-functional
Description:	Multi-criteria decision analysis shall be used to help select the optimal strategies and rank their options.		
Source:	Description of the action (page 153)		

ID:	MCA02	Title:	Scope of MCDA
Priority:	High	Type:	Non-functional
Description:	Multi-criteria decision analysis shall take multiple objectives (e.g. inputs generated by the impact assessment models, economic evaluation methodology and qualitative analysis of broader societal changes) into account.		
Source:	Description of the action (page 83)		

ID:	MCA03	Title:	Application of specific algorithms
Priority:	Medium	Type:	Non-functional
Description:	A variety of algorithms should be considered to be processed, e.g. weighted sum model, weighted product model, superiority and inferiority ranking method, stochastic multi-criteria acceptability analysis, rough set approach, best worst method, analytic hierarchy process, analytic network process, etc.		
Source:	Description of the action (page 153)		

ID:	MCA04	Title:	MCEA – data processing
Priority:	Medium	Type:	Non-functional
Description:	In the multi-criteria analysis model all qualitative conditions/criteria should be quantified and expressed as numbers, so that the potential MCEA algorithms described by the mathematical equations and formulas could be applied.		
Source:	Partners within the consortium		

5.7 Dissemination, exploitation and commercialisation

This section presents the requirements that should be taken into account during the design and development of the DSS to facilitate the increasing awareness of the DISTENDER project among the interested public and private institutions.

ID:	DEC01	Title:	Providing information about the DISTENDER project in reports
Priority:	Medium	Type:	Non-functional
Description:	Reports generated in the DSS should contain information about their development as part of the DISTENDER project results.		
Source:	Partners within the consortium		

ID:	DEC02	Title:	Providing information about the DISTENDER project in the system
Priority:	Medium	Type:	Non-functional
Description:	The DSS should provide information about the project in which it was developed and about the funding agency.		
Source:	Partners within the consortium		

ID:	DEC03	Title:	Availability of a working server with the system
Priority:	High	Type:	Non-functional
Description:	The working server with the system shall be available on the Internet for authorized users during the project for demonstration purposes and possibly two years after the project.		
Source:	Description of the action (page 134)		

ID:	DEC04	Title:	Storing DISTENDER results
Priority:	High	Type:	Non-functional
Description:	The DSS shall deposit the DISTENDER results as a research data repository accessible free of charge under a creative commons license for third parties to mine, exploit, reproduce and disseminate.		
Source:	Description of the action (page 133)		

ID:	DEC05	Title:	Including knowledge generated by DISTENDER
Priority:	High	Type:	Non-functional
Description:	The knowledge generated by DISTENDER will be offered by a Decision Support System (DSS) which will include guidelines, manuals, easy-to-use tools and experiences from the application of the cases studies.		
Source:	Description of the action (page 9)		

5.8 Others

Other requirements that do not fit the previous groups of requirements are collected in this section.

ID:	O1	Title:	Allowing users to familiarize themselves with the system
Priority:	Medium	Type:	Functional
Description:	The system should enable potential users to see its basic functions and the results they can receive by creating a New User account with the possibility of working on synthetic data.		
Source:	Partners within the consortium		

ID:	O2	Title:	Providing a New User with publicly available data
Priority:	High	Type:	Non-functional
Description:	The system shall not enable a New User to follow the data which are not publicly available in the DISTENDER project (e.g. should not present or generate data which were developed within another CCS and are restricted).		
Source:	Partners within the consortium		

ID:	O3	Title:	User-friendliness
Priority:	Medium	Type:	Non-functional
Description:	The system should be simple (user-friendly) in terms of inputs and provide clear outputs. The system should be easy to navigate with a user-friendly interface.		
Source:	Users		

ID:	O4	Title:	Saving results for editing and for further processing
Priority:	Medium	Type:	Functional
Description:	The system should enable the results to be saved and displayed or edited again.		
Source:	Partners within the consortium		

ID:	O5	Title:	Creating account and its management
Priority:	Medium	Type:	Functional
Description:	The user should be able to ask for creating an account in the system and manage it in an easy way.		
Source:	Partners within the consortium		

ID:	O6	Title:	Saving a user's project
Priority:	Medium	Type:	Non-functional
Description:	The system should allow the user to save his own project with settings of predefined preferences.		
Source:	Partners within the consortium		

ID:	O7	Title:	User project management
Priority:	Medium	Type:	Non-functional
Description:	The user should be able to edit/change the project on his own and remove it when necessary.		
Source:	Partners within the consortium		

ID:	O8	Title:	System availability
Priority:	Medium	Type:	Non-functional
Description:	The system should be available through a web application.		
Source:	Partners within the consortium		

ID:	O9	Title:	Providing guidance related to the use of the system
Priority:	Medium	Type:	Functional
Description:	The system should provide guide how to use specific functions.		
Source:	Partners within the consortium		

ID:	O10	Title:	Providing user-friendly help
Priority:	Medium	Type:	Functional
Description:	The system should provide user-friendly help which will guide users how to do certain activities. Help topics should be indexed and provide full text search feature.		
Source:	Partners within the consortium		

ID:	O11	Title:	Monitoring main indicators of strategy implementation
Priority:	Low	Type:	Functional
Description:	The system may provide a dashboard that monitors the main indicators of a strategy implementation and sends warning signals when intermediate steps are not achieved.		
Source:	Users		

ID:	O12	Title:	Differentiation of measures
Priority:	Low	Type:	Functional
Description:	The system may separate mitigation from adaptation measures and show the results depending on whether the strategy requires mitigation or adaptation actions.		
Source:	Users		

ID:	O13	Title:	Differentiation of the end users
Priority:	Low	Type:	Non-functional
Description:	Many different kind of users may have an access to the system to support the decision maker in the decision making process.		
Source:	Users		

6 Conclusions

Two main results emerged from the work carried out as part of collecting user requirements. The first one are collected and described requirements defined by potential users of the system as well as the consortium partners. Thanks to cooperation with the representatives of end users, who are also the project partners, these requirements can be verified and updated on an ongoing basis. The second, equally important result is updated mock-up reflecting the way the system may work (presented below). However, it is worth emphasizing that the visualization of a potential system presented below is for illustrative purposes. The final design of the system will be proposed at a later stage of the project.

STEP1: Case Study selection

The screenshot shows the 'DECISION SUPPORT SYSTEM' logo in the top left corner. A dark blue header bar contains the text 'STEP1: Case Study selection' on the right. Below the header, there are two main interactive elements: a dropdown menu on the left and a button on the right. The dropdown menu is open, displaying a list of case study options: 'The Metropolitan City of Turin', 'Austria', 'Guimarães', 'Dehesas (Spain) and montados (Portugal)', and 'The North-east of The Netherlands'. The button on the right is labeled 'Add your case study'.

STEP2: Selection of the strategies in which the user is interested in

The screenshot shows the 'DECISION SUPPORT SYSTEM' logo in the top left corner. A dark blue header bar contains the text 'STEP2: Strategy selection' on the right. Below the header, there is a single large dropdown menu. The dropdown menu is open, displaying a list of strategy options: 'Strategy a: Strategy for consumption and soil waterproofing', 'Strategy b: Adaptation and resilience to climate change', 'Strategy c: Improve ecological functionality & increase forest areas', 'Strategy d: Energy efficiency and district heating', and two lines of '....' indicating more options. The dropdown menu has a small downward arrow icon on its right side.

STEP3: Relevance (the user specifies how important the particular indicators are)

DECISION SUPPORT SYSTEM STEP3: Relevance

The following indicators are applicable:

- Indicator A: mortality
- Indicator B: land use change
- Indicator C: CO2 concentration
- Indicator D: money-saving
- Indicator E: (no text label)

Specify how important they are to you.

Each indicator has a slider from 1 to 5. In the image, Indicator A is set to 2, Indicator B to 3, Indicator C to 2, Indicator D to 4, and Indicator E to 3.

STEP 4: Obtaining the results - the user receives a set of robust strategies (ranked according to their compliance with the user's preferences), that can be implemented along with information about their impact on various aspects (land use, sectors, economy, etc)

DECISION SUPPORT SYSTEM STEP4: results - list of strategies

The system proposes the following robust strategies:

Order	The name of the robust strategy	Mitigation and adaptation measures which were applied in the specific strategy	Impact	Costs	Socio economic effects
1	Strategy d	Show	Show	Show	Show
2	Strategy g	Show	Show	Show	Show
3	Strategy b	Show	Show	Show	Show

STEP5: Generating a comprehensive report

The screenshot shows the 'DECISION SUPPORT SYSTEM' logo in the top left corner. A dark blue header bar contains the text 'STEP5 as an option: generating the report'. Below this, a button labeled 'Generate the report' is centered. The main content area is divided into two columns. The left column, titled 'Include', lists several report components: 'My preferences/relevance of indicators', 'The list of adaptation and mitigation measures', 'The impact on sectors', 'The maps', 'The diagrams of changes', and 'The socio-economic effects', followed by three ellipses. The right column, titled 'All', contains a vertical stack of seven square checkboxes, with the top three containing a downward-pointing chevron symbol.

